

Optimizing formulation and development of amlodipine-indapamide bilayer film-coated tablets with *in vitro* dissolution equivalence to a reference drug

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop and optimize a bilayer tablet containing immediate-release amlodipine and sustained-release indapamide for the treatment of hypertension. Using BCPharSoft OPT software, individual layer formulations were optimized: 8.63% croscarmellose sodium for the amlodipine layer and 32.41% HPMC K15M with 4.51% PVP K30 for the indapamide layer. The final bilayer tablets exhibited hardness between 230 N and 260 N and a 3% weight gain after film coating, which had no significant effect on drug release. A validated HPLC–DAD method, following ICH guidelines, confirmed the accurate quantification of both drugs across pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8. The method demonstrated high specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. Overall, the formulation achieved *in-vitro* dissolution equivalence to a reference commercial product.

Keywords

amlodipine, indapamide, bilayer tablet, HPLC–DAD, formulation optimization

Introduction

Hypertension (high blood pressure) is a common condition that causes health problems and requires lifelong ther-

apy. Hypertension has become increasingly prevalent, and its global burden has grown over time, primarily driven by population growth, lifestyle changes, and aging (Dzau and Balatbat 2019). Indeed, the number of adults aged ≥ 20 years

worldwide with hypertension was approximately 1.39 billion in 2010, comprising 694 million men and 694 million women (Mills et al. 2016). The hypertension population in low- and middle-income countries was almost three times higher than that in high-income countries (1.04 billion vs. 349 million) (Mills et al. 2016). Hypertension can promote cerebrovascular disease, heart failure, coronary artery disease, chronic kidney disease, and reduced quality of life. More seriously, hypertension can also cause severe neurological sequelae such as hemiplegia and a vegetative state (Dzau and Balatbat 2019), and over 19% of all deaths in 2015 were associated with elevated systolic blood pressure (>115 mmHg) (Dzau and Balatbat 2019).

The combined drug therapy has been found to improve blood pressure control in patients with hypertension (Farooq and Ray 2015; Williams et al. 2018). This therapy typically involves angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) or angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), along with thiazide diuretics or calcium channel blockers (Iqbal and Jamal 2023). A recent approach to simplify and enhance the efficiency of hypertension treatment is the use of two or more active ingredients in a single dosage form (Yousefbour et al. 2015; Akhtar et al. 2020). Amlodipine besylate is a calcium channel inhibitor of the dihydropyridine group, while indapamide is a thiazide-like diuretic used in the treatment of decompensated heart failure and hypertension (Farooq and Ray 2015; Williams et al. 2018). The combination therapy of immediate-release amlodipine besylate and sustained-release indapamide has been shown to improve blood pressure reduction and limit excessive diuretic effects, primarily owing to angiotensin I receptor blocking activity and diuretic action (Kobalava et al. 2022). In addition, this formulation not only stabilizes blood pressure over 24 hours but also reduces treatment time and improves patient compliance (Jadhav et al. 2014). However, the detailed formulations and manufacturing protocols of commercial products are typically undisclosed. Meanwhile, the development of a generic drug combining amlodipine and indapamide remains limited, hindering affordable access to this effective hypertension treatment, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Therefore, research aimed at developing generic formulations containing amlodipine-indapamide is essential to achieving effective and economical hypertension treatment using fewer excipients and lower manufacturing costs.

Data from the literature show that the presence of amlodipine and indapamide has been quantified to facilitate the monitoring and regulation of pharmaceutical products (Narmada et al. 2009; Rai et al. 2012; Hossain et al. 2013). Additionally, the formulation of amlodipine besylate or indapamide tablets was investigated through the preparation and optimization processes (Begum et al. 2011; Alam et al. 2017). The outcomes of these studies have consistently demonstrated *in vitro* equivalence in the testing dissolution media as compared to the brand-name drug (Begum et al. 2011; Alam et al. 2017).

This study aims to develop the formulation of the bilayer tablet that can achieve an *in vitro* equivalence

compared to the reference drug. In this study, we use a high-performance liquid chromatography-photodiode array, also known as diode array detector (HPLC-DAD) detection method because it is a simple, rapid, accurate, and effective method for determining small amounts of analytes such as curcumin in floating tablets (Huynh et al. 2023a), antibiotics (Huynh et al. 2023b), and pharmaceuticals and toxic impurities (Rahman et al. 2022). To the best of our knowledge, no studies have been published on the formulation optimization of bilayer tablets with sustained-release indapamide and immediate-release amlodipine in all three dissolution pH media of 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8. Moreover, conducting a quantitative analysis of the dissolution medium for the active components and assessing their dissolution in buffer solutions is an essential task during drug development. This study presents the formula optimization of amlodipine-indapamide bilayer tablets, which achieve *in vitro* equivalence to a reference commercial drug. This study has the potential to serve as a valuable reference in the field of pharmaceutical science and industry, particularly in regions with limited resources, where there is a growing interest in developing generic drugs based on established formulations.

Materials and methods

Materials

The active pharmaceutical ingredients included amlodipine (content 99.5%, Cadila Healthcare Ltd., Ahmedabad, India) and indapamide (content 99.7%, Suzhou Lixin Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., Suzhou, China). Excipients included hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) K15M (Colorcon, USA), polyvinylpyrrolidone K30 (Povidone, Ludwigshafen Land, Rheinland-Pfalz, Germany), aerosil (Evonik Industries AG, Essen, Germany), sodium croscarmellose (SCC, Mingtai Chemical Co., Ltd., Taoyuan, Taiwan), sodium starch glycolate (DST, Roquette, Lestrem, France), dicalcium phosphate anhydrous and maltodextrin (A Tab, Innophos, New Jersey, USA), microcrystalline cellulose (MCC, Huzhou City Linghu Xinwang Chemical Co., Ltd., Huzhou, China), lactose monohydrate (Kemphasol, Mumbai, India), magnesium stearate (Evolutics International Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad, India), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) 6 cps (Colorcon, USA), titanium dioxide (Sukhmani Impex, Punjab, India), and macrogol-PEG 6000 (Evolutics International Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad, India). Distilled water and 96% alcohol (Vietnam) were also used.

Indapamide (97.7% purity; Batch No. QT264 020121) and amlodipine besylate (103% purity; Batch No. QT145 120122), used as internal standards, were obtained from the Institute of Drug Quality Control, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

The reference commercial drug was Natrixam® (Les Laboratoires Servier Industrie Company, France; Lot No. 6052969; expiry date 01/2024).

The mobile phase components for high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) included acetonitrile (ACN, Fisher Scientific, New Hampshire, USA), methanol (Sigma-Aldrich, Massachusetts, USA), triethylamine (TEA, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and phosphoric acid (Xilong Scientific Co., Ltd., Guangdong, China), all of which met the prescribed analytical standards.

Instrumentations

The equipment used in this study included a KB 15S cube mixer (Erweka, Langen, Germany), GT granulate and powder flow tester (Erweka, Langen, Germany), PTB hardness tester (Pharma Test, Hainburg, Germany), PTF E abrasion tester (Pharma Test, Hainburg, Germany), PTWS 120D dissolution apparatus (Pharma Test, Hainburg, Germany), ABS 220-4 electronic scale (Kern & Sohn GmbH, Baden-Württemberg, Germany), Cadpress II tablet press (CMC Machinery, Ahmedabad, India), and FSC-20 film coating machine (Tien Tuan, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam). For analysis, an Agilent HPLC–DAD (Agilent Technologies, Inc., California, USA) was used with a Luna C18 (250 × 4.0 mm, 5 μm) column (Phenomenex Inc., Torrance, USA). An HI 2550 pH meter (Hanna Instruments Ltd., Leighton Buzzard, England) and an AES 220-4 analytical balance (accuracy of 0.1 mg; Kern & Sohn GmbH, Baden-Württemberg, Germany) were also utilized. Tablets were produced using a Rimek 12-punch rotary tablet press (Karnavati Engineering Ltd., Kadi, India). Microsoft Excel (version 2021, Microsoft, USA) was used for statistical analysis.

Methods

Development of HPLC–PDA method for quantitative analysis of amlodipine and indapamide in various dissolution conditions

Method development

Chromatographic analysis was conducted using a Luna C18 column (250 × 4.0 mm, 5 μm; Phenomenex Inc., Torrance, USA) with a flow rate of 1 mL/min, injection volume of 50 μL, and column temperature maintained at 40 °C. The wavelength range scanned was 200–400 nm, and both amlodipine and indapamide showed maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 242 nm, which was selected for analysis. The mobile phase initially included ACN, methanol (MeOH), and 0.8% TEA aqueous solution (pH 3.0, adjusted with 10% phosphoric acid). Optimal chromatographic conditions were achieved with a mobile phase composition of ACN:MeOH:0.8% TEA (42:3:55, v/v/v), providing retention times of approximately 4.3 minutes for amlodipine and 6.0 minutes for indapamide.

Sample preparation

Stock standard solutions of amlodipine (200 μg/mL) and indapamide (100 μg/mL) were prepared by dissolving the

accurately weighed standards in methanol as the diluent. Working standard solutions, containing amlodipine (10 μg/mL) and indapamide (1.5 μg/mL), were obtained by precise dilution of the stock standard solutions to the desired concentrations using the same diluent. All standard solutions were filtered through a 0.45-μm membrane filter prior to chromatographic analysis.

Sample solutions were prepared by randomly selecting 20 film-coated tablets, followed by determination of the average weight and content of each tablet. An accurately weighed amount of homogenized powder equivalent to the average tablet weight was dissolved and diluted in a 50 mL volumetric flask using a mixture of methanol and dissolution medium. The desired concentration was obtained by further diluting the prepared solution in a 10 mL volumetric flask. The blank solution consisted of a mixture of methanol and dissolution medium. The placebo solution was prepared by mixing a precise quantity of excipients with a minimal amount of methanol in a 50 mL volumetric flask. The remaining volume was filled with the dissolution medium. Then, 500 μL of the resulting solution was accurately transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted with the dissolution medium to obtain the working placebo solution.

Through intensive investigation, optimal chromatographic conditions were established using a mobile phase composed of acetonitrile: methanol: 0.8% triethylamine aqueous solution (pH 3.0, adjusted with 10% phosphoric acid) in a ratio of 42:3:55. The separation was carried out on a Luna C18 (250 × 4.0 mm, 5 μm) column at a flow rate of 1 mL/min, injection volume of 50 μL, and a column temperature of 40 °C. Detection was performed using a photodiode array detector at 242 nm.

Method validation

Method validation was conducted according to the guidelines of the ICH (1995).

System suitability

System suitability was evaluated by injecting the standard solution and sample solution six times. The system meets suitability criteria when the relative standard deviation (RSD) is less than 2.0%, the discordance coefficient of the amlodipine and indapamide peaks falls within the range of 0.8–1.5, and the resolutions between the peaks of amlodipine, indapamide, and other components are greater than 1.5.

Specificity

The method is considered specific when the chromatograms of the mobile phase solution, dissolution medium, and placebo solution show no peaks at retention times corresponding to those of the standard sample. Additionally, the test sample chromatogram must display peaks at retention times consistent with those of

the standard sample. Furthermore, the chromatogram of spiked test samples must exhibit increased peak height and area, with retention times equivalent to those of the standard sample.

Linearity

Mixed standard solutions of amlodipine and indapamide were prepared to yield various concentrations of amlodipine (2, 4, 8, 10, and 12 µg/mL) and indapamide (0.3, 0.6, 1.2, 1.5, and 1.8 µg/mL). The resulting data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel software to determine the regression equation and correlation coefficient (R^2). The process achieves linearity as $0.995 \leq R^2 \leq 1$.

Precision

Method precision includes repeatability and intermediate precision. These were determined using six sample solutions containing each analyte at approximately 100% of the target concentration, analyzed on the same day and on two different days, respectively. The method is considered precise when the RSD of the analytes, both within a single day and across two days, is less than 2.0%.

Accuracy

Exact amounts of reference amlodipine and indapamide were mixed with the placebo matrix to prepare spiked solutions at three concentration levels: 80%, 100%, and 120% of the target concentration. Three replicate samples were prepared and analyzed at each level. The percentage recovery and RSD of the added analytes were calculated for each replicate. The method is considered accurate when the recovery falls within the range of 95–105% and the RSD does not exceed 2.0%.

Stability

A system suitability test was conducted each time the method was used, either before or during analysis. The stability of the analyzed solution was evaluated by storing it at room temperature for 4, 8, 12, 24, 36, and 48 h and comparing its chromatographic spectrum with that of a freshly prepared standard solution. The solution was considered stable if the variations in analyte peak areas between the stored sample and the freshly prepared standard were less than 2%. Throughout the tested storage period, the analyte peak areas in both the standard and sample solutions were required to remain within $\pm 2\%$ of the initial values.

Robustness

The robustness of the analytical method reflects its ability to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters. In this study, changes in flow rate, temperature, and the pH of the buffer in the mobile phase were evaluated. The method was deemed robust, as these variations did not significantly affect the analytical performance.

Formulation design and optimization

Dissolution of Natrixam[®] reference tablet

Details of the dissolution conditions are provided in Table 1. At each time point, 10 mL of the solution was withdrawn, filtered through a 0.45-µm membrane filter, and analyzed using HPLC–DAD under the previously described optimal chromatographic conditions. The relative standard deviation (RSD) was calculated from six test samples. At each time point, the acceptable RSD is $\leq 10\%$ for active ingredient release below 85% and $\leq 5\%$ for release above 85% (Das et al. 2012; United States Pharmacopoeial Convention 2020).

Table 1. The dissolution tests were conducted under specified experimental conditions (*), using six tablets in 1000 mL of buffer solution at 37 ± 0.5 °C.

Buffer solution	pH = 1.2	pH = 4.5	pH = 6.8
Temperature (°C)		37 ± 0.5	
Stirring speed (rpm)	75	100	100
Sampling time (min or h)	10, 15, 30, 45, 60 min	2, 4, 8, 12, 16 h	2, 4, 8, 12, 16 h

*Conditions for dissolution tests (Das et al. 2012; United States Pharmacopoeial Convention 2019a, b, 2020).

The formula design and optimization of the immediate-release amlodipine layer

The immediate-release amlodipine formulation was prepared using fixed formulation ingredients and the direct compression method. The composition included 13.88 mg of amlodipine besylate, 57 mg of A Tab, 2 mg of Aerosil, 1.5 mg of magnesium stearate, and 212.94 mg of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), combined in an appropriate volume. The excipients under investigation were superdisintegrants: sodium croscarmellose in formulas F1–F5 and sodium starch glycolate in formulas F6–F10. The quantities tested are listed in Table 2.

Ten formulations, denoted as F1–F10, were prepared. The independent variable x_1 represented the type of superdisintegrant—sodium croscarmellose (SCC) or sodium starch glycolate (SSG), while x_2 represented the quantity of the superdisintegrant excipient used in each formulation.

Table 2. Contents of sodium croscarmellose and sodium starch glycolate in formulas F1–F10.

Materials	Formulation (mg/tablet)									
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Sodium croscarmellose (SCC)	10.65	12.78	14.91	17.0	19.16					
Sodium starch glycolate (DST)						10.65	12.78	14.91	17.0	19.16

The dependent variable was the dissolution of amlodipine from the tablets at 10, 15, 30, 45, and 60 min in a dissolution medium at pH 1.2. These responses were denoted as $\bar{y}_1, \bar{y}_2, \bar{y}_3, \bar{y}_4$, and \bar{y}_5 , respectively.

The formula design and optimization of the sustained-release indapamide layer

The sustained-release indapamide formulations were prepared using the wet granulation method with fixed formula ingredients, including 1.5 mg of indapamide, 0.82 mg of Aerosil, 0.8 mg of magnesium stearate, and 190 mg of lactose monohydrate, each in appropriate quantities. The primary variables examined in the formulations were the polymer hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K15M) and the adhesive excipient polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K30). The detailed composition of each formulation is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Composition of formulas F11–F30 for the development of the sustained-release indapamide layer.

Formula	HPMC K15M (mg)	PVP K30 (mg)	Formula	HPMC K15M (mg)	PVP K30 (mg)
F11	38.00	5.70	F21	66.50	5.70
F12	38.00	6.65	F22	66.50	6.65
F13	38.00	7.60	F23	66.50	7.60
F14	38.00	8.55	F24	66.50	8.55
F15	38.00	9.50	F25	66.50	9.50
F16	57.00	5.70	F26	76.00	5.70
F17	57.00	6.65	F27	76.00	6.65
F18	57.00	7.60	F28	76.00	7.60
F19	57.00	8.55	F29	76.00	8.55
F20	57.00	9.50	F30	76.00	9.50

For the 20 formulations from F11 to F30, the independent variables were defined as x_3 (HPMC K15M content) and x_4 (PVP K30 content). The $\bar{y}_6, \bar{y}_7, \bar{y}_8, \bar{y}_9$, and \bar{y}_{10} represent the dissolution of indapamide from tablets in a pH 4.5 medium at time points of 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 h, respectively. Similarly, $\bar{y}_{11}, \bar{y}_{12}, \bar{y}_{13}, \bar{y}_{14}$, and \bar{y}_{15} correspond to the dissolution of indapamide in a pH 6.8 medium at the same time points.

The bilayer tablet formulation containing immediate-release amlodipine and sustained-release indapamide

The bilayer tablets were prepared using the wet granulation method for the sustained-release indapamide layer and the direct compression (straight stamping) method for the immediate-release amlodipine layer. Four formulations of bilayer tablets (H1, H2, H3, and H4) were developed with varying hardness levels of 220, 230, 250, and 260 N, respectively. The dissolution profiles of these formulations were compared with that of the reference product. The optimal hardness range was determined by evaluating the similarity of dissolution profiles using the similarity factor f_2 algorithm. The f_2 formula is given by (Liu et al. 1997):

$$f_2 = 50 \log \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (R_t - T_t)^2 \right)^{-0.5} \times 100 \right\}$$

The variable n represents the total number of sampling points. R_t denotes the average percentage of the control drug that has dissolved at a given time t measured from the beginning of the test. T_t represents the average percentage of the reagent that has dissolved at time t since the start of the test. A prerequisite for this study is that the value of f_2 must fall within the range of 50–100.

Film-coated bilayer tablets containing amlodipine and indapamide

After examining the film-coating excipients, the optimal film-coating formula was determined to consist of 6.98 mg HPMC 6 cps, 0.70 mg PEG 6000, 1.40 mg magnesium stearate, 2.92 mg titanium dioxide, 50 mg water, and 100 mg alcohol. The following process parameters were investigated: inlet air temperature of 55–60 °C, outlet air temperature of 45–50 °C, pan speed of 0.5–8 rpm, spraying speed of 10–40 mL/min, and spray gun pressure of 0.5–2.5 bar. The film-coating procedure consisted of the following steps: (1) weighing and grinding the components separately; (2) gently stirring the polymer in hot water at 70 °C for 15 min using magnetic stirring, followed by the gradual addition of the remaining ingredient mixture to the polymer solution; (3) filtering the resulting mixture through a 0.4-mm sieve to obtain the film-coating solution; (4) drying and weighing the tablets before coating; and (5) cooling and drying the coated tablets. A weight gain of 3% per tablet after the coating process was required and achieved, and the coated tablets met the appearance criteria. Additionally, the effect of film coating on tablet dissolution was evaluated. Dissolution tests were performed in three buffer solutions (pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8) before and after film coating, and the results were compared statistically.

Results

Development of an HPLC-DAD method for simultaneous determination of amlodipine and indapamide in three different pH buffers

System suitability parameters

The relative standard deviation (RSD) of the retention time, peak area, and theoretical plate number for both amlodipine and indapamide was less than 2.0% (Suppl. material 1: table S1). The peak asymmetry factor (As) for both compounds ranged from 0.8 to 1.5, indicating acceptable peak symmetry and confirming the column's effective separation performance. The resolution (Rs) between amlodipine and indapamide exceeded 1.5, demonstrating sufficient separation of the two analytes on the chromatogram, thereby allowing their reliable qualitative

and quantitative determination. With $A_s > 0.8$ and $R_s > 1.5$, the dissolution testing method met the system suitability criteria in accordance with guidelines from the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH Q2(R1)) (1995), the European Medicines Agency (EMA) (2014), and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (2021).

Specificity

Fig. 1 presents the chromatograms obtained at three buffer pH levels—1.2, 4.5, and 6.8—for the specificity study. Under identical chromatographic conditions, the chromatograms of the blank, placebo, and mobile phase solutions exhibited no peaks at the retention times of amlodipine and indapamide. In contrast, the chromatograms of the sample solutions displayed two distinct peaks at retention times corresponding to those of amlodipine and indapamide. Furthermore, the chromatograms of the matrix-spiked samples showed two peaks with increased height and area relative to the corresponding peaks in the sample chromatograms. These results confirm the specificity of the developed HPLC–DAD method.

Linearity, range, precision, and accuracy of the developed method

The results for linearity, range, precision, and accuracy of the method in dissolution tests across the three pH buffer conditions (1.2, 4.5, and 6.8) are shown in Suppl. material 1: table S2. The linearity ranges were 2–12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for amlodipine and 0.3–1.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for indapamide. The coefficient of determination (R^2) exceeded 0.998 for both analytes, indicating an excellent linear correlation between analyte concentration and peak area. Additionally, the RSD values for assay results of amlodipine and indapamide in both repeatability and intermediate precision assessments were below 2.0%. The recovery values for both analytes were within 95–105% of the labeled amount, thereby confirming the accuracy and reliability of the method (ICH 1995). These results also support the repeatability and intermediate precision of the method in all three dissolution media. In other words, the method demonstrated precision within acceptable limits (RSD < 2.0%). Furthermore, the recovery rates remained within 95–105%, and the RSD values were

below 2.0% for both analytes across all three pH levels, confirming the accuracy of the developed method.

This HPLC–PDA method offers the advantage of a short sample run time and the capacity to process large sample volumes, significantly reducing overall analysis time. Therefore, it is well-suited for routine pharmaceutical industry applications.

Stability of standard and sample solutions at three buffer pHs of 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8

The stability of standard and sample solutions of amlodipine and indapamide was evaluated at three buffer pH levels (1.2, 4.5, and 6.8) over a 48-hour period at room temperature (Suppl. material 1: table S3). The relative standard deviation (RSD) remained below 2.0% for all measurements, confirming that both solutions are stable for at least 48 hours under these conditions.

Robustness

The developed HPLC–DAD method demonstrated robustness, as minor deliberate variations in flow rate, column temperature, and mobile phase buffer pH did not significantly impact system performance. The RSD values remained within acceptable limits ($\leq 2.0\%$) (Suppl. material 1: table S4).

The formula design and optimization of bilayer tablets containing immediate-release amlodipine and sustained-release indapamide

The dissolution of the *Natrixam*[®] reference drug

The dissolution profiles of amlodipine and indapamide from the reference product (*Natrixam*[®]) across various time points met the regulatory RSD requirements specified by ICH, EMA, and FDA guidelines (ICH 1995; United States Pharmacopoeial Convention 2019a, b). The dissolution results of the reference drug revealed the minimum and maximum intervals of the released active components (i.e., amlodipine and indapamide) in the three pH media and within the

Figure 1. Chromatograms of (a) mobile phase, (b) blank, (c) placebo, (d) sample, (e) standards, and (f) matrix spike.

investigated intervals (Table 4). These intervals of values serve as the basis for establishing the values of the dependent variables, denoted as \bar{y}_1 – \bar{y}_{15} during the optimization process, particularly in the following required manners: \bar{y}_1 (93–94%), \bar{y}_2 (94–95%), \bar{y}_3 (95–96%), \bar{y}_4 (96–97%), \bar{y}_5 (98–100%), \bar{y}_6 (10–15%), \bar{y}_7 (15–35%), \bar{y}_8 (35–55%), \bar{y}_9 (55–75%), \bar{y}_{10} (75–100%), \bar{y}_{11} (10–15%), \bar{y}_{12} (15–35%), \bar{y}_{13} (35–55%), \bar{y}_{14} (55–75%), \bar{y}_{15} (75–100%) (ICH 1995; FDA 2021; EMA 2014).

For the reference drug, the resulting dissolution values of amlodipine in pH 4.5 and 6.8 media exhibited no substantial disparity across various time points. Consequently, the dissolution values obtained in pH 1.2 medium were selected for use in achieving maximum optimization.

Formula optimization of immediate-release tablet containing 10 mg amlodipine

The experimental results (Table 5) served as the input data for the BCPharSoft OPT software to assess the correlation between the independent and dependent variables. The dependent variables were subjected to constraint conditions, requiring the measured dissolution values at pH 1.2 over time intervals of 10, 15, 30, 45, and 60 minutes to fall within the following specified ranges: \bar{y}_1 (93–94%), \bar{y}_2 (94–95%), \bar{y}_3 (95–96%), \bar{y}_4 (96–97%), and \bar{y}_5 (98–100%).

Fig. 2 illustrates the dissolution outcomes for the amlodipine layer across various time intervals ranging from

Table 4. Dissolution values of amlodipine (Amlo) and indapamide (Inda) released from the reference commercial drug over time at three different pH levels.

Ingredient	Amlo	Inda								
pH = 1.2										
Time (min)	10		15		30		45		60	
Average (%)	93.60	-	94.87	-	95.13	-	96.73	-	98.93	-
RSD (%)	1.21	-	0.72	-	0.63	-	0.53	-	0.39	-
pH = 4.5										
Time (h)	2		4		8		12		16	
Average (%)	98.29	13.73	98.49	19.86	98.61	41.86	98.64	62.21	98.81	83.70
RSD (%)	0.28	1.06	0.36	1.13	0.35	3.88	0.29	2.89	0.25	1.82
pH = 6.8										
Time (h)	2		4		8		12		16	
Average (%)	98.36	14.65	98.52	16.34	98.28	52.02	98.38	68.31	98.55	85.26
RSD (%)	0.47	1.26	0.36	1.78	0.28	0.44	0.24	0.54	0.40	0.51

Figure 2. Formula optimization for the amlodipine layer using the BCPharSoft OPT; the amlodipine dissolution results at various time intervals. (a) 10 minutes (y_1), (b) 15 minutes (y_2), (c) 30 minutes (y_3), (d) 45 minutes (y_4), (e) 60 minutes (y_5).

Table 5. Experimental results of dissolution values in pH 1.2 for the amlodipine layer.

Formula	Variable		Amlodipine dissolution (%)				
	x_1	x_2	\bar{y}_1	\bar{y}_2	\bar{y}_3	\bar{y}_4	\bar{y}_5
1	1	5	79.6	82.3	83.1	85.4	87.5
2	1	6	82.7	83.8	86.4	87.4	89.4
3	1	7	85.4	86.1	87.6	88.8	90.4
4	1	8	94.5	95.1	95.9	96.4	97.2
5	1	9	96.7	95.7	96.1	97.4	98.6
6	2	5	72.6	75.3	75.1	78.4	80.5
7	2	6	75.7	75.8	79.4	79.4	82.4
8	2	7	77.4	79.1	80.6	81.8	83.4
9	2	8	80.3	80.7	80.5	81	83.1
10	2	9	84.6	85.6	86.5	87.1	87.5

Note: x_1 represents the types of superdisintegrant excipients; $x_1 = 1$ is sodium croscarmellose (SCC), and $x_1 = 2$ is sodium starch glycolate (DST). x_2 is the percentage of superdisintegrant excipient (%) in each formula. $\bar{y}_1, \bar{y}_2, \bar{y}_3, \bar{y}_4,$ and \bar{y}_5 are the solubilities (%) of the amlodipine layer over 10, 15, 30, 45, and 60 min, respectively.

10 to 60 minutes. In this context, x_1 was assigned a value of 1, indicating the use of croscarmellose sodium, while x_2 ranged between 8.6% and 9%, satisfying the specified criteria for the dependent variable ranges.

Optimal parameters: $x_1 = 1$ and $x_2 = 8.627\%$.

Predictive properties: $\bar{y}_1 = 92.439\%$, $\bar{y}_2 = 93.325\%$, $\bar{y}_3 = 95.316\%$, $\bar{y}_4 = 95\%$, $\bar{y}_5 = 95.795\%$.

Both the R^2 train and R^2 test values generated by the software exceeded 0.9, confirming the model's high predictive accuracy. Consequently, the model was utilized for investigation, optimization, and prediction of the causal-dependent variables.

The optimal formula comprised 13.88 mg amlodipine besylate, 18.36 mg SCC, 57 mg dicalcium phosphate anhydrous and maltodextrin (A Tab), 2 mg aerosil, 1.5 mg magnesium stearate, and 120.2 mg microcrystalline cellulose. Subsequently, 1000 tablets were prepared based on the above formula ingredients. The optimal results predicted by the BCPharSoft OPT software were experimentally verified, as shown in Table 6.

Comparison of the experimental mean values and predicted values using ANOVA yielded $F = 2.3$, which is less than $F_{crit} = 5.32$. This indicates that the obtained experimental results are consistent with the predicted results by BCPharSoft OPT software.

Formula optimization of the sustained-release layer containing 1.5 mg indapamide

For the indapamide layer, pH media of 4.5 and 6.8 were selected for calculating dissolution values for

formulation optimization, as the dissolution of active ingredients at pH 1.2 was insufficient to yield reliable results. The outcomes were entered into the BCPharSoft OPT software to assess the correlation between independent and dependent variables.

The dependent variable was subjected to constraint conditions, namely the measured solubilities in the two pH media (4.5 and 6.8) at 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 hours, respectively (Table 7). These conditions encompass the following: \bar{y}_6 (10–15%), \bar{y}_7 (15–35%), \bar{y}_8 (35–55%), \bar{y}_9 (55–75%), \bar{y}_{10} (75–100%), \bar{y}_{11} (10–15%), \bar{y}_{12} (15–35%), \bar{y}_{13} (35–55%), \bar{y}_{14} (55–75%), and \bar{y}_{15} (75–100%).

Suppl. material 1: figs S1, S2 depict that x_3 ranged between 30% and 34%, while x_4 ranged from 3% to 5%, meeting the specified criteria for the dependent variable ranges.

Optimal parameters: $x_3 = 32.408\%$ and $x_4 = 4.512\%$.

Predictive properties: $\bar{y}_6 = 13.651\%$, $\bar{y}_7 = 15.065\%$, $\bar{y}_8 = 48.068\%$, $\bar{y}_9 = 66.49\%$, $\bar{y}_{10} = 79.222\%$, $\bar{y}_{11} = 14.991\%$, $\bar{y}_{12} = 16.164\%$, $\bar{y}_{13} = 51.677\%$, $\bar{y}_{14} = 68.703\%$, $\bar{y}_{15} = 82.392\%$.

The R^2 train and R^2 test values provided by the software exceeded 0.9, confirming the suitability of the prediction model. Thus, the model was used for investigating, optimizing, and predicting causal dependent variables.

Therefore, the optimal formula consisted of 1.5 mg indapamide, 61.58 mg HPMC K15M, 8.57 mg PVP K30, 0.82 mg Aerosil, 0.8 mg magnesium stearate, and 116.74 mg lactose monohydrate. Then, we prepared 1000 tablets using the formula ingredients. The optimal results predicted by BCPharSoft OPT software were experimentally verified (Table 8).

By comparing the experimental mean values and the predicted values using ANOVA, the result is $F = 0.01 < F_{crit} = 4.41$, so the obtained experimental results are consistent with those predicted by BCPharSoft OPT software.

The research tablets demonstrated indapamide release in both pH 4.5 and pH 6.8 dissolution media, adhering to the Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetic model, with correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.9743 and 0.9702, respectively (Suppl. material 1: table S5). Similarly, the release of indapamide from the reference drug also conformed to the Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetic model in both pH 4.5 and pH 6.8 media, with correlation coefficients of 0.9967 and 0.9725, respectively (Suppl. material 1: table S5). Hence, the active ingredient release kinetics of the research tablets and reference tablets are equivalent in both pH 4.5 and pH 6.8 dissolution media.

Table 6. Amlodipine released from the optimal formulation: experimental versus predicted data.

Amlodipine release % over time (min)	Verification results						Prediction
	Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3	Average (%)	SD (%)	RSD (%)	
10	90.451	92.528	94.943	92.64	2.25	2.43	92.439
15	95.422	94.365	96.418	95.40	1.03	1.08	93.325
30	96.225	96.119	97.285	96.54	0.64	0.67	95.316
45	97.190	98.250	98.191	97.88	0.60	0.61	95.000
60	99.811	98.770	98.775	99.12	0.60	0.60	95.795

Table 7. Experimental results for the indapamide layer.

Formula	Variable		Indapamide dissolution (%)									
	x_3	x_4	\bar{y}_6	\bar{y}_7	\bar{y}_8	\bar{y}_9	\bar{y}_{10}	\bar{y}_{11}	\bar{y}_{12}	\bar{y}_{13}	\bar{y}_{14}	\bar{y}_{15}
1	20	3	29.4	55.4	73.4	94.7	98.8	32.4	56.4	75.4	96.7	99.8
2	20	3.5	27.3	50.3	70.3	93.2	97.3	29.3	52.3	72.3	95.2	99.3
3	20	4	24.4	46.6	68.7	93.3	96.7	26.4	48.6	69.7	94.3	98.7
4	20	4.5	22.9	42.2	64	90.4	96.1	23.9	44.2	65	92.4	98.1
5	20	5	18.3	39.9	60.3	89.5	95.8	20.3	40.9	62.3	91.5	97.8
6	30	3	19.3	33.9	56.6	67.8	95.7	21.3	35.9	57.6	68.1	96.7
7	30	3.5	17.2	30.5	52.3	66.9	94.5	19.2	31.5	54.3	67.9	95.8
8	30	4	15.6	25.8	49.7	66	93.9	17.6	27.8	51.7	67	94.9
9	30	4.5	14.3	21.4	45.6	65	93.6	15.3	23.4	47.6	67.1	94.6
10	30	5	11.4	17.6	43.5	64.1	91.4	13.4	19.6	44.5	66.1	93.4
11	35	3	15.9	21.3	49.6	67.6	89.6	16.1	22.3	51.6	68.6	90.1
12	35	3.5	14.6	20.3	48.4	66.9	88.1	14.7	21.6	49.4	67.9	89.4
13	35	4	14.1	19.8	45.6	65.4	87.6	13.5	20.3	47.6	66.4	88.6
14	35	4.5	13	19.3	44.3	64.6	87.1	13.1	19.8	45.6	65.1	87.3
15	35	5	12.5	17.9	41.8	62.1	85.1	12.7	18.9	43.8	64.1	86.1
16	40	3	13.1	15.6	19.9	46.8	64.3	13.7	15.7	20.9	47.8	65.1
17	40	3.5	11.7	13.9	18.7	44.8	63.3	11.9	13.9	19.7	46.8	64.3
18	40	4	10.3	12.6	16.7	44.1	61.4	10.6	12.8	18.7	45.1	63.4
19	40	4.5	-	10.7	15.5	39	58.1	-	10.9	16.5	40	60.1
20	40	5	-	-	14.7	36.6	57.3	-	-	15.7	37.6	59.3

Note: x_3 is the quantity of HPMC K15M, and x_4 is the quantity of PVP K30 in each formula. $\bar{y}_6, \bar{y}_7, \bar{y}_8, \bar{y}_9, \bar{y}_{10}, \bar{y}_{11}, \bar{y}_{12}, \bar{y}_{13}, \bar{y}_{14}, \bar{y}_{15}$ are the dissolution (%) of the indapamide layer in pH = 4.5 (\bar{y}_6, \bar{y}_{10}) and pH = 6.8 ($\bar{y}_{11}, \bar{y}_{15}$) over 2 h, 4 h, 8 h, 12 h, and 16 h.

Table 8. Indapamide layer verification and prediction results.

Indapamide release % over time		Verification result						Prediction	Reference drug
		Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3	Average (%)	SD (%)	RSD (%)		
pH = 4.5	2 h	15.198	14.682	13.671	14.52	0.78	5.35	13.651	13.73
	4 h	17.103	16.021	15.082	16.07	1.01	6.29	15.065	19.86
	8 h	48.901	46.035	48.051	47.66	1.47	3.09	48.068	41.86
	12 h	68.512	66.395	65.42	66.78	1.58	2.37	66.49	62.21
	16 h	81.235	80.301	78.245	79.93	1.53	1.91	79.222	83.70
pH = 6.8	2 h	16.213	14.935	15.291	15.48	0.66	4.26	14.991	14.65
	4 h	18.235	18.178	17.218	17.88	0.57	3.20	16.164	16.34
	8 h	51.625	53.688	50.612	51.98	1.57	3.02	51.677	52.02
	12 h	70.801	68.835	67.793	69.14	1.53	2.21	68.703	68.31
	16 h	83.401	82.382	80.432	82.07	1.51	1.84	82.392	85.26

Bilayer formulation of immediate-release amlodipine and sustained-release indapamide

The bilayer tablets were prepared using the optimized formulations of indapamide and amlodipine. The indapamide layer was created through wet granulation followed by compression, ensuring sustained release. The amlodipine layer, designed for immediate release, was added via direct compression. Details of the technological flow for the bilayer tablet production are presented in Suppl. material 1: fig. S3. The hardness values of bilayer tablets were determined using H_1 - H_4 equations, which in turn provided f_2 value results in three dissolution test media (pH = 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8) (Table 9).

Film-coated bilayer tablets containing amlodipine and indapamide

The film-coated tablets met the criteria for weight gain and attractiveness. Furthermore, the dissolution profiles of the tablets were evaluated both before and after film coating. The results indicated that the coating

Table 9. The f_2 value of the formulated tablets compared to the reference commercial drug.

Formula	Hardness (N)	pH = 1.2		pH = 4.5		pH = 6.8	
		Amlo	Inda	Amlo	Inda	Amlo	Inda
H1	220	60.36	-	96.15	47.71	92.26	45.81
H2	230	75.69	-	93.65	57.69	92.26	60.32
H3	250	79.18	-	83.61	74.99	87.88	79.77
H4	260	72.54	-	81.97	50.83	88.61	51.53

film did not significantly alter the release profiles of either amlodipine or indapamide (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4 shows the appearance of the produced amlodipine-indapamide bilayer film-coated tablets, which appear to be highly uniform in shape, size, and color.

Discussion

The hardness of the formulated bilayer tablets, ranging from 230 to 260 N, met the required criteria, as evidenced

Figure 3. The influence of the coating film on the release characteristics of amlodipine and indapamide from bilayer tablets.

Figure 4. A photo of our produced amlodipine-indapamide bilayer film-coated tablets.

by the achieved f_2 values comparable to those of the reference drug. In the amlodipine layer, the superdisintegrant excipient plays a crucial role in achieving the desired release conditions of the active ingredient at specific investigation time points (Desai et al. 2013). Several studies have mentioned the use of superdisintegrant excipients such as cross-povidone, SCC, and DST (Desai et al. 2013; Khadka et al. 2021). In this study, the tablets containing amlodipine and SCC exhibited stable and satisfactory dissolution compared to the other two excipients (Srikanth et al. 2013). DST has also been extensively studied and found to yield positive results in tablet formulations of amlodipine in some studies (Rai et al. 2012; Desai et al. 2013). Khadka et al. (2016) mentioned the use of SCC and DST at different concentrations in the formulation of 18 formulas, in which 8% SCC provided the maximum drug release within 10 min and was the most effective formulation. Therefore, an appropriate range for SCC and DST superdisintegrant excipients was determined to be 5–9%. Notably, the direct compression method offers numerous advantages, such as time savings, a simple preparation process, and reduced labor requirements, while ensuring product quality (Sheraz et al. 2016; Alam et al. 2017; Khadka et al. 2021). Hence, it was chosen for the preparation of the amlodipine layer in this study. SCC with a content of 8.627% demonstrated *in vitro* equivalent results to the control drug in the three different pH media of 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8.

The indapamide layer necessitates the sustained release of the active ingredient over 24 hours. Given the

minimal indapamide content in the tablets, the wet granulation method ensures even distribution of the active ingredient, meeting requisite quality standards (Becker et al. 1997). Adhesive excipients are an essential prerequisite for the wet granulation method and are currently prevalent, such as gelatin, cellulose, cellulose derivatives, polyvinylpyrrolidone, starch, sucrose, and polyethylene glycol (PEG). These excipients bind granule powders, facilitating solid tablet adhesion. However, an improper quantity of adhesive excipients can impede the release of the active ingredient. This study used PVP K30 as the adhesive excipient owing to its high mechanical strength, good stability, and favorable impact on the release of the active ingredient (Srikanth et al. 2013). Since the amount of PVP in the range of 0.25–6% is recognized as suitable for adhesion, a ratio of 3–5% was selected to ensure high tablet solidity with minimal interference in the release of the active ingredient. To attain the objective of a stable release of the active ingredient over a specific time-frame, the most crucial component in the formulation is the polymer. Various polymers (e.g., HPMC, xanthan gum, carbomer) have been employed for sustained-release medications, each with distinct properties, advantages, and disadvantages. HPMC K15M offers numerous advantages, including resilience against external factors such as humidity, light, and temperature, and the absence of a distinctive taste. Previous studies have noted HPMC K15M as a scaffolding excipient that provides appropriate release levels, meets final product requirements, and achieves *in vitro* release levels comparable to those of the original drug with HPMC K15M amounts of 32.35% and 25% (Hossain et al. 2013; Alam et al. 2017).

The BCPharSoft OPT software is utilized to optimize formulas, thereby expediting the research process and enhancing precision. Moreover, the analysis of cause-and-effect relationships aids in the accurate examination of influencing factors, thereby facilitating convenient and effortless formula adjustments. To optimize the amlodipine layer's formula, the survey parameters of amlodipine were chosen at a pH of 1.2 due to the significant variability in values at different time points and across survey formulas compared to the other two pH media of 4.5 and 6.8. For the indapamide layer's formula, the dissolution values at time points of 2 h, 4 h, 8 h,

12 h, and 16 h in the two pH media of 4.5 and 6.8 served as the data for optimization. The result of 32.41% HPMC K15M aligns with the findings of Hossain et al. (2013), who used 32.35% HPMC.

The initial step involves the preparation of the indapamide layer, which demonstrates stability in terms of sensory properties and tablet parameter quality, rendering it convenient during the stamping procedure. The release of active ingredients is influenced by the hardness of the tablet (Seitz and Flessland 1965). The tested hardness for bilayer tablets ranged from 220 to 260 N (Table 6), and the tablet quality was evaluated by comparing its hardness value with that of the control drug via the f_2 value. The satisfied hardness range was 230–260 N, as the f_2 indices exceeded 50. The broad acceptable hardness range makes it easier to achieve the final qualified drug products during the production process. This study not only successfully developed an HPLC-DAD method for the quantitative analysis of amlodipine and indapamide in three different dissolution pH conditions but also optimized the formulation of amlodipine–indapamide bilayer tablets. Thus, it establishes a foundation for the next steps of upscaling production and the development of generic drugs for hypertension treatment.

During the film coating process, an inlet air temperature ranging from 55 to 60 °C was utilized, along with a coating fluid formulation consisting of HPMC 6 cps and PEG 6000, both known for their relatively high viscosity, which could potentially hinder the release of active ingredients. As depicted in Fig. 3, the dissolution of the post-film coating across pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8 media exhibited a slight decrease. However, this difference was not statistically significant (with p-values of 0.87, 0.99, and 0.98 for the pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8 media, respectively). This lack of significance can be attributed to the active ingredients' insensitivity to the specified temperature range. Moreover, HPMC K15M, which has the most significant influence on indapamide release, possesses a high melting temperature (345–500 °C) (Soni et al. 2015). Consequently, a mere 3% weight gain was observed after the film coating, which had a negligible impact on the release properties of the two active substances.

Conclusion

In this study, a formulation of bilayer film-coated tablets containing immediate-release amlodipine and sustained-release indapamide was successfully optimized. The developed formulation met *in vitro* dissolution equivalence across three pH media—1.2, 4.5, and 6.8—when compared to a reference commercial drug. This study establishes a foundation for the next steps of upscaled production and the development of

economical generic antihypertensive drugs for low- and middle-income countries.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

D.T.M.H.: Methodology, conceptualization, writing—original draft, project administration, resources, writing—review and editing, supervision S.T.K.: Methodology, conceptualization, writing—original draft, data curation, resources, writing—review and editing, T.D.N., Q.H.N., T.D.T.N., A.D.Q.N., N.N.K.N., M.T.A.N., L.K.H., M-N.T.L., T.V.N.: Investigation, data curation, analysis, writing—review and editing, P.H.L.: Supervision, data curation, writing—review and editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary information

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